

rare earths in the present case. The trend of stability constants of binary as well as ternary complexes follows the order $\text{Sc(III)} > \text{Y(III)} > \text{Sm(III)} > \text{Nd(III)} > \text{Pr(III)} > \text{La(III)}$ i. e., stability decreases with the increase in ionic radii.

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References

1. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397; 1954, 2904.
2. S. D. MAKHIJANI and S. P. SANGAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 788.
3. S. D. MAKHIJANI and S. P. SANGAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 448.
4. S. D. MAKHIJANI and S. P. SANGAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15A, 1977.

Kinetics of Oxidation of Succinic Acid by Cerium(IV) Sulphate in Acidic Medium

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THE Survey of the literature shows that a systematic kinetic study of the oxidation of aliphatic acids like oxalic^{1,2}, malonic³⁻⁵, succinic and glutaric acids has not received any attention so far. The present study deals the oxidation of succinic acid by cerium(IV) in presence of sulphuric acid.

Experimental

The chemicals used were either "AnalaR or E. Merck" guaranteed reagent quality. Cerium(IV) sulphate solution was prepared by dissolving ceric sulphate (Fluka, A. R.) in sulphuric acid. The reactive substances were brought to the thermostat temperature maintained to $\pm 0.1^\circ$ and then rapidly mixed. Aliquots were withdrawn at known intervals of time and reaction was quenched by adding ice-cold distilled water and the unconsumed cerium(IV) was estimated with standard solution of Mohr's salt using ferroin as an indicator. The pseudo first order rate constant k was determined from the graph by plot of $\log [\text{unconsumed Ce(IV)}]$ Vs. time (t).

The order of reaction has been determined with the help of Vant Hoff's differential equation and comes out to be less than one w.r.t. Ce(IV) and succinic acid. Further the pseudo first order behaviour of the reaction w.r.t. succinic acid has been confirmed by plotting $1/k$ vs. $1/[\text{succinic acid}]$. The plot is a straight line which does not pass through the origin but it cuts $1/k$ axis at a certain distance (Fig. 1). This suggests an information of activated complex between Ce(IV) and succinic acid.

Fig 1

Effect of Sulphuric Acid

The effect of sulphuric acid on the reaction has been studied at five different concentrations of sulphuric acid as shown in Table-1.

TABLE - 1

$10^3 \times [\text{Ce(IV)}] = 0.20M$; $10^3 \times [\text{Succinic acid}] = 1.50M$;
Temp. = 60°

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25
$10^3 \times k (\text{min}^{-1})$	8.14	6.85	5.62	5.20	2.26

The plot of k vs. $1/[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]^2$ is a straight line which indicates that the rate of reaction is inversely proportional to the square of the concentration of sulphuric acid.

